

1 **Running Title:** Habitat suitability of *C. elburzensis* and *C. hotsoni*

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3 **Landscape and niche specialization of two brush tailed mice species *Calomyscus elburzensis***
4 **and *C. hotsoni* in Iran: a case of the role of ecological niche modelling in finding area(s) of**
5 **contact**

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20 **Abstract**

21 Brush-tailed mice (family Calomyscidae) are small rodents found on the Iranian plateau and
22 surrounding areas. To date, little discussion of the ecological aspects, habitat suitability and
23 niche differentiation has been provided for members of this family. Herein, to model the
24 potential distributions and describe habitat preferences of *Calomyscus elburzensis* and *C.*

25 *hotsoni*, the maximum entropy modelling (MaxEnt) approach was used based on data collected
26 through field expeditions, review of the literature and various database. Species distribution
27 modelling showed that minimal temperature of the coldest month and precipitation of the coldest
28 quarter were the most important factors in predicting the distribution of *C. elburzensis*. However,
29 occurrence of *C. hotsoni* was affected greatly by isothermality and annual precipitation. The
30 mountainous regions in northeastern Iran, the central portions of the Elburz Mts, and the eastern
31 hillsides of the Zagros Mts were identified as the most suitable habitats for *C. elburzensis*,
32 whereas the western parts of South Khorasan province, the forest steppes in the southeast of Iran,
33 and the southwestern extension of the Jebal Barez Mts in central Iran were highly suitable for *C.*
34 *hotsoni*. Measurement of ecological niche overlaps showed low similarity between the niches of
35 these two species. Nevertheless, the modelling identified areas of suitable habitat in the north
36 center parts of both South Khorasan and Kerman provinces where both or either of these species
37 could occur. Moreover, *C. elburzensis* inhabited cold mountains, Mediterranean, and cold semi-
38 desert climatic conditions, whereas *C. hotsoni* was generally showed high level of habitat
39 suitability to hot dry desert and hot semi-desert climatic conditions. *C. elburzensis* mainly
40 inhabits forest steppe and semi-desert biotopes, whereas *C. hotsoni* occupies desert lowlands in
41 addition to forest steppe and semi-desert biotopes. Further studies are needed to resolve the
42 distribution of each species and to follow their interactions in potential contact zones.

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44 KEY WORDS: niche differentiation, habitat suitability, ecological niche modelling, contact zone,
45 Rodentia, Calomyscidae.

46

47

INTRODUCTION

48 An ecological niche can be defined as all the resources and environmental conditions that are
49 necessary for a species to maintain a viable population (MacArthur 1972). Each species uses an
50 ecological niche, which may vary, often with considerable overlap, among different geographic
51 areas, seasons, habitats, and/or food resources. The term niche differentiation is synonymous
52 with niche segregation, niche separation or niche partitioning and all refer to the process by
53 which natural selection drives competing species into different patterns of resource use or
54 different niches. Spatial niche differentiation may be described as a form of habitat separation
55 which may serve as a mechanism for species coexistence in resource-limited systems (Scott &
56 Dunstone 2000; Zhong et al. 2016). Hence, coexistence of two species might happen through
57 mechanisms that avoid competitive exclusion, such as resource partitioning or niche separation,
58 especially when food resources are limited (Illoldi-Rangel et al. 2004; Holt 2009).

59 Small terrestrial mammals including some rodents are very poor at dispersing across altitudinal
60 and habitat barriers, only a few miles in breadth (Bowers & Brown 1982). There is a positive
61 relationship between the actual size and shape of the home range and body size of the animal
62 (e.g. Kelt & Van Vuren 1999) or the productivity of food (e.g. carnivores have larger home
63 ranges than omnivores or herbivores of similar body size; Lindstedt et al. 1986). Since rodents
64 generally have small home ranges, it is common to observe several species which potentially
65 interact within a relatively small geographic areas (Brown 1971; Lindstedt et al. 1986; Kelt &
66 Van Vuren 1999).

67 Geographic structure of contact zones influences the dynamic of the evolutionary processes
68 (Cardozo & Chiaraviglio 2008). Morphological similarities among coexistence species suggests
69 potential interactions that may result in niche differentiation where ecologically similar species
70 may diverge in their landscape-scale habitat use (Cardozo et al. 2012). In contrast, competitive
71 exclusion between closely related species is proposed to prevent range overlap and therefore

72 could maintain parapatric distributions when species have diverged due to geographical isolation
73 but retained the same environmental niche (niche conservatism). However, secondary contact
74 following range expansion may result in morphological or ecological character displacement
75 (Brown & Wilson 1956) in the contact zone where the species are in sympatry. This could result
76 in a differentiation of their environmental niche on each side of their common boundary
77 (Ricklefs 2010). Thus, greater differences in environmental niches in cases of sympatry are
78 expected compared to allopatric distributions (Dayan & Simberloff 2005; Wiens & Graham
79 2005). All in all, species distributions result from interactions of ecological and evolutionary
80 factors including abiotic restrictions, dispersal limitations, interspecific competitions, and local
81 adaptations. Competitive interference is likely responsible for discontinuous distributions, local
82 allopatry, of similar species. Hence coexistence or local sympatry and geographical and local
83 allopatry are of interest to systematists for a better understanding of evolutionary processes and
84 phylogenetic inferences (Rychlik 2005).

85 Brush-tailed mice (family Calomyscidae Vorontsov & Potapova 1979) are small rodents found in
86 rocky outcrops and semi-mountainous areas in desert regions of Iran, Turkmenistan,
87 Afghanistan, Pakistan, Azerbaijan, and Syria (Musser & Carleton 2005; Kilpatrick 2017).
88 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*C. elburzensis* Goodwin 1938) has been reported from
89 mountains of northern and northeastern Iran, eastern parts of the Yazd province (Iran), western
90 Iran in Zanzan and Esfahan provinces, southwestern and southern Turkmenistan and
91 northwestern Afghanistan (Lebedev et al. 1998; Musser & Carleton 2005; Hamidi et al. 2015,
92 2016; Akbarirad et al. 2016b; Kilpatrick 2017; Yusefi et al. 2019). This species is found in
93 barren, dry and rocky habitats in mountains with Mediterranean spring rains and in other areas
94 with cold winters and little vegetation (winters are milder at lower elevation sites). In the Elburz
95 Mts, near the northeastern parts of its distribution, habitat has been reported as rocky outcrops

96 with numerous cracks on steep ridges and steep mountain slopes (Hamidi et al. 2016; Shenbrot &
97 Molur 2016; Kilpatrick 2017). Hotson's brush-tailed mouse (*C. hotsoni* Thomas 1920) has been
98 recorded from eastern, southern and southeastern parts of Iran (including Hormozgan, Kerman
99 and desert mountain range of Sistan and Baluchestan provinces), and southwestern regions of
100 Pakistan (Musser & Carleton 2005; Norris et al. 2008; Khajeh et al. 2015; Kilpatrick 2017;
101 Yusefi et al. 2019). Recently this species has been reported from the South Khorasan province, in
102 the northeast of Iran (Akbarirad et al. 2016a; Hamidi et al. 2016). This species is found in arid
103 rocky habitats and dry rocky mountain tops with sparse shrubby vegetation and it may be
104 restricted to the Saharo-Sindian phylogeographic region which is characterized by hot, dry
105 summers and mild winters (Norris et al. 2008; Kilpatrick 2017).

106 Taxonomic studies of Goodwin's and Hotson's brush-tailed mice have had a long history and
107 have documented biological (Meyer & Malikov 1995, 1996; Hamidi et al. 2015, 2017, 2018),
108 morphological (Musser & Carleton 2005; Malikov et al. 2006; Shahabi et al. 2011; Hamidi et al.
109 2017), molecular (Norris et al. 2008; Shahabi et al. 2013; Akbarirad et al. 2016a, 2016b; Hamidi
110 et al. 2016) and karyological (e.g. Graphodatsky et al. 2000; Meyer & Malikov 2000; Malikov et
111 al. 2001; Shahabi et al. 2010) differences. In contrast, very little is known of their habitat,
112 ecological requirements and interactions either in the wild or in captivity (e.g. Lay 1967; Habibi
113 1977; Nowak 1999; Hamidi et al. 2016, 2018) and no studies have been conducted to compare
114 the habitats used by these two species.

115 In this study, we aimed to describe the potential distribution and habitat suitability and to
116 determine possible niche overlap between these two species of brush-tailed mice. A maximum
117 entropy modelling (MaxEnt) approach was used to construct potential distribution maps based on
118 presence data and climatic variables (Phillips et al. 2006). Environmental niche modelling, also
119 known as ecological niche modelling, species distribution modelling, predictive habitat

120 distribution modelling, and climate envelope modelling has allowed advances in the knowledge
121 of geographic ecology of species, ecological and evolutionary determinants of spatial patterns of
122 biodiversity and detects areas of endemism, range shifts in response to climate change, as well as
123 inferences of speciation processes and species delimitation (Elith et al. 2006; Rissler & Apodaca
124 2007; Elith & Leathwick 2009). The known distribution of Goodwin's and Hotson's brush-tailed
125 mice has been expanded greatly in the past 15 years (Kilpatrick 2017; Yusefi et al. 2019), thus
126 use of ecological niche modelling will characterize the niche of these two species to predict other
127 areas where these two taxa may occur.

128 In general, these two species are similar in their external morphology (general body size and
129 phenotypic characteristics), as well as their nesting habits and preferred habitats (Hamidi et al.
130 2016; Kilpatrick 2017). It is hypothesized that resource partitioning or interspecific interactions
131 would occur where they coexist. Although no areas of contact are currently known, these two
132 species have been reported to occur at localities less than approximately 100 km apart in the
133 northern parts of South Khorasan province in Iran. Due to close approximation of the southern
134 extension of the range of *C. elburzensis* and northern extension of the range of *C. hotsoni*,
135 similarities observed in the landscape of these two areas, and the absence of any obvious
136 potential geographic barrier, it is likely that these two species may be found in contact or may
137 have occurred in contact in the past or even may occur in contact in the future in this region of
138 Iran.

139

140 MATERIALS AND METHODS

141 *Study area*

142 Sampling area was located in eastern Iran (25-38°N and 55-63°E), which is an ideal region for
143 the study of landscape-scale niche differentiation of small rodents because of the documented

144 diversity with 30 species of rodents (Darvish & Rastegar-Pouyani 2012; Hamidi et al. 2016)
145 including members of the Calomyscidae. Eastern Iran is located in the arid belt and is separated
146 from other regions of Iran by topographic barriers such as Kopet-Dag Mts ranging to the north
147 and two large deserts, Dasht-e-Lut to the south and Central Kavir to the west (Darvish &
148 Rastegar-Pouyani 2012). Heights in the eastern parts of Iran consist of numerous chains of
149 mounts: (1) Binalud- Ala-Dag heights as an eastern extension of Elburz Mts mainly located in
150 North Khorasan province, (2) southern extension of Kopet-Dag Mts with its main heights, Hezar
151 Masjed- Allāho Akbar located in northeastern most part of Iran, (3) Chehel Tan Mts and Khaje-
152 Morad heights in the center of Razavi Khorasan province, (4) toward the west, heights include
153 Shirkuh Mts located in the center of Iran, south of Yazd province, and Jebal Barez Mts in
154 Kerman province, (5) Bon-Dar Mts with the Darmian heights in the east and Bagheran Mts with
155 two main heights named Ark, and Shadan and Olang in the west which are in South Khorasan
156 province, (6) Taftan Mts in the southeastern most part of Iran near the Iran-Pakistan border, and
157 (7) Bashagard heights southwest of Taftan toward the south extension of Zagros Mts
158 (Darvishzadeh 2003; Aghanabati 2004).

159 The climatic conditions in eastern Iran include Mediterranean with spring rains, cold mountains,
160 cold semi-desert, hot semi-desert, dry desert, hot dry desert and coastal dry areas, with a variety
161 of biotopes such as forest steppe, forest and woodland, semi-desert and desert lowland (Islamic
162 Republic of Iran Meteorological Organization Site, at <http://www.irimo.ir>). In the northeast,
163 winters are relatively cold with medium snowfall (average annual precipitation is only 277 mm
164 in areas with greater humidity). Spring and fall are mild, while summers are relatively dry and
165 hot. The typical vegetation of northeast Iran is Greek juniper (Cupressaceae; *Juniperus excelsa*
166 M. Bieb.), Mount Atlas pistache (Anacardiaceae; *Pistacia atlantica* Desf.), dog rose (Rosaceae;
167 *Rosa canina* L.), sun spurge (Euphorbiaceae; *Euphorbia helioscopia* L.), shrubby horsetail

168 (Ephedraceae; *Ephedra* sp.) and berberry shrubs (Berberidaceae; *Berberis integerrima* Bunge) as
169 well as cover of blessed milk thistle [Asteraceae; *Silybum marianum* (L.) Gaertn.], and harmel
170 peganum (Zygophyllaceae; *Peganum harmala* L.). In southeastern Iran, winters are mild, and
171 summers are very hot. Sparse shrubby vegetation is typical, consisting mainly of bushes of
172 shrubby horsetail, common oat (Poaceae; *Avena sativa* L.), Mount Atlas pistache and dwarf
173 mazari palm [Arecaceae; *Nannorrhops ritchieana* (Griff.) Aitch.]. Generally, the vegetation was
174 denser at higher latitudes and sparser at lower latitudes in the eastern parts of Iran (Hamidi et al.
175 2016).

176 *Field work and trapping method*

177 Trapping sessions were performed during January 2013 and April 2018 using custom-made mesh
178 live traps baited with suitable food types. Trapping was carried out for 39 trials (approximately
179 1000 trap-nights). Traps were set in the late afternoons and checked initially in the following
180 mornings. Date, sex, body weight and approximate age of all captured individuals were recorded.
181 Plant coverage, elevation, climatic conditions, geographical and environmental variables,
182 geological and geomorphological features such as soil type, and overall habitat structure were
183 also recorded for each sampling locality during field expeditions. Data on burrow and feeding
184 signs of the rodents were also collected.

185 In total, six rocky areas and 36 trapping stations in eastern Iran were monitored in this study
186 based on previous findings on the preferred habitat types, geological zones and soil structures
187 used by brush-tailed mice. Due to insufficient records from northeastern parts of the distribution
188 range of *C. elburzensis* in Iran, near the Iran-Turkmenistan border, and also northern most
189 extension of the distribution range of *C. hotsoni*, these localities were selected for sampling
190 [identified in Table 1 as Hamidi et al. 2016, 2017, and unpublished data (K. Hamidi)]. These
191 areas included the Binalud-Ala-Dag heights (2 stations; 6 *C. elburzensis* captured), Hezar

192 Masjed- Allāho Akbar heights (9 stations; 6 *C. elburzensis* captured) (Fig. 1A-B), Khaje-Morad
193 heights (6 stations; 48 *C. elburzensis* captured), Darmian heights (4 stations; no *Calomyscus*
194 captured), Bagheran Mts (10 stations; 5 *C. hotsoni* captured) (Fig. 1C-D), and finally, Taftan Mts
195 (5 stations; 1 *C. hotsoni* captured).

196 In total, 60 individuals of *C. elburzensis* and 6 of *C. hotsoni* were captured. Captured brush-
197 tailed mice were examined for any signs of diseases and overall welfare before being transferred
198 to the animal house where each was kept in a separate cage to ensure their good health before
199 further experiments such as mating trials. They were maintained in captivity for different
200 investigations including biological (K. Hamidi unpublished data), developmental (Hamidi et al.
201 2017), and behavioral studies in captivity (Hamidi et al. 2018). Some of them were released in
202 their home range when the project was finished.

203 Species identification was carried out based on morphological and morphometric characters
204 using identification keys and distinguishing characteristics (Corbet 1978; Etemad 1984;
205 Kilpatrick 2017), and also molecular studies (Table 1). Specimens were deposited in the
206 Research Group of Rodentology, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran. Animal care and
207 experimental procedures were performed in compliance with the “Guideline for the care and use
208 of laboratory and experimental animals, Rodentology Research Group, Ferdowsi University of
209 Mashhad”.

210 *Data collection and point localities*

211 Distribution data (collecting locality coordinates) for these two species of brush-tailed mice were
212 obtained from available literature records (Hassinger 1973; de Roguin 1988; Graphodatsky et al.
213 2000; Norris et al. 2008; Shahabi et al. 2010; Akbarirad et al. 2015, 2016a, 2016b; Khajeh et al.
214 2015; Hamidi et al. 2016, 2017; Safapour 2017; Haddadian Shad & Darvish 2018a, 2018b), and

215 databases (<https://www.gbif.org/> and <http://www.vertnet.org/>). A total of 65 and 22 localities of
216 presence were identified for *C. elburzensis* and *C. hotsoni*, respectively (Table 1).

217 *Modelling of species distribution and landscape analyses*

218 Environmental variables predictors including nineteen bioclimatic layers (Bio1-19) obtained
219 from the WorldClim database (<http://www.worldclim.org/>) were used as independent variables.

220 All layers were downloaded as 30 arc-second (~ 1 km) resolution, and then cropped using
221 ArcGIS v. 10.3 (ESRI) to include Iran, Turkmenistan, Afghanistan and Pakistan boundaries.

222 Environmental layers and records were applied in OpenModeller v. 1.0.7 (de Souza Muñoz et al.
223 2011) to obtain the relevant grid values for each record.

224 A multi-collinearity test was conducted using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) in SPSS v. 16.0
225 (SPSS Inc. 2007) to identify the variables with correlations greater than 0.75. Variables with
226 correlations lower than 0.75 were chosen for inclusion in species distribution models (Table 2).

227 Maximum entropy modelling (MaxEnt v. 3.3.3e) (Phillips et al. 2006) was employed to assess
228 the environmental factors at localities where these two species of brush-tailed mice occur and to
229 predict suitable regions for the presence of these species. Ten percent of the data were used as
230 test data and the rest were considered as training data. Maximum number of iterations of 500
231 with a 0.00001 convergence threshold, and a multiplier regularization of 1 were used for running
232 models. MaxEnt was run 10 times for each species in order to obtain averages of predictions
233 (Phillips et al. 2006). The area under receiver-operating-characteristic curves (AUCs) was
234 considered as the criterion for model accuracy and acts as a measure for the model's
235 discrimination ability to indicate present points from absent ones in a procedure that is
236 independent from suitability thresholds (Elith et al. 2011). The value of AUC ranges between 0
237 and 1. A model with no predictive ability should return an AUC of 0.5; an AUC greater than 0.5

238 indicates that the model is better than random; and a value close to 1 indicates near perfect
239 accuracy of the model (Phillips & Dudík 2008).

240 ENMTools v. 1.0 was also used to examine Schoener's D statistic for calculating niche overlap
241 among the two species (Warren et al. 2010). ASCii files for each species obtained from MaxEnt
242 analysis were applied in ENMTools for computing the niche overlap. The value of Schoener's D
243 index ranges between 0 and 1, in which the value of 0 means that ecological niches do not have
244 any overlap, and values close to 1 indicate high similarity between ecological niche models and
245 hence, the ecological niches are considered as identical (Schoener 1968).

246

247

RESULTS

248 A total of 12 layers of bioclimatic variables were selected to run the model in MaxEnt (Table 2).
249 The mean AUC value for testing data was 0.896 ± 0.0491 for *C. elburzensis* and 0.9201 ± 0.0329
250 for *C. hotsoni*. The minimal temperature of the coldest month with a percentage contribution
251 value (PC) of 48.22% and permutation importance value (PIMP) of 49.41%, and the
252 precipitation in the coldest quarter (PC = 26.06%, PIMP = 27.08%) had the greatest effects on
253 the final model for *C. elburzensis*. However, the niche model for *C. hotsoni*, was affected greatly
254 by isothermality (PC = 55.52%, PIMP = 16.03%) and annual precipitation (PC = 23.58%, PIMP
255 = 34.32%).

256 The niche modelling showed that the highest probability for the presence of *C. elburzensis* was
257 in environments with the precipitation of the coldest quarter between 70 and 90 mm. However,
258 the niche model for *C. hotsoni*, identified areas with annual precipitation between 100 and 200
259 mm as the most suitable ones. Moreover, with increasing the isothermality values, the probability
260 of the presence of this species decreased.

261 According to the maps generated, northeastern Iran (Binalud-Ala-Dag heights, Kopet-Dag Mts
262 and Hezar Masjed-Allāho Akbar heights, as well as heights in central Razavi Khorasan), central
263 parts of the Elburz Mts, and eastern parts of Zagros Mts (especially northern parts of Jebal Barez
264 Mts in Kerman province) were identified as the most suitable habitats for *C. elburzensis* (Fig. 2),
265 whereas only forest steppes in the southeastern Iran (Sistan and Baluchestan province) were
266 predicted as the most suitable habitats for *C. hotsoni* (Fig. 3). Furthermore, the Jebal Barez Mts
267 in central Iran (north center of the Kerman province) and areas of north center of the South
268 Khorasan province were considered as possible contact zones for these two species and areas
269 where they might be found in sympatry (Figs. 2-3).
270 However, the Schoener's D metric value was calculated as 0.299631 which indicated that these
271 two species show a low similarity between their ecological niches.

272

273

DISCUSSION

274 Species distribution models generally reveals the realized ecological niche of a species and
275 describes the environmental conditions in which a species is able to survive and reproduce in the
276 presence of biotic interactions, such as predation and symbiosis (Hutchinson 1957; Elith et al.
277 2006; Rissler & Apodaca 2007; Elith & Leathwick 2009). Since recently evolved lineages often
278 cannot be readily recognized using traditional species criteria (concepts), a diversity of
279 approaches has been used for species delineation (e.g., fixed or non-overlapping differences in
280 morphological, behavioral, and ecological characters, levels of molecular divergence, reciprocal
281 monophyly or geographic isolation) (e.g. see Blair et al. 2013, Braz et al. 2018). Thus, ecological
282 niche modelling offers a great potential for detecting ecologically mediated parapatric speciation,
283 when the environmental gradient variables driving speciation are included in the ecological niche
284 modelling (de Queiroz 1998).

285 *Distribution range and habitat suitability*

286 The ecological niche models identified suitable climatic condition for *C. elburzensis* to occur
287 mainly in the mountainous and higher regions of northern, northeastern and central Iran whereas
288 the climatic conditions for the occurrence of *C. hotsoni* were found in the hot and dry regions of
289 southeastern Iran. The predictive habitat distribution model for *C. hotsoni* suggests that suitable
290 habitats extend from the southeastern most parts of Iran, near the type locality of the Hotson's
291 brush-tailed mouse in southwestern Pakistan, northward to the western parts of the South
292 Khorasan province and the southwestern extension of the Jebal Barez Mts in the Kerman
293 province. The Central Kavir and Dasht-e-Lut are geographic barriers to the dispersal of both
294 species. *C. elburzensis* are connected by habitats north of the Central Kavir, whereas regions east
295 and west of the Dasht-e-Lut inhabited by *C. hotsoni* are connected by habitats south of the
296 Dasht-e-Lut.

297 Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse is distributed in the Elburz Mts, Binalud-Ala-Dag heights, Kopet-
298 Dag Mts, Chehel Tan Mts and Bon-Dar Mts in the northeast, Shirkuh and Jebal Barez Mts in
299 central Iran, and towards west Karkas and Ghaflankooch, whereas *C. hotsoni* has been recorded
300 from the Bagheran and Taftan Mts and the Bashagard heights in the southeast Iran (see Hamidi
301 et al. 2016 for more details). According to the tectonic map of Iran (Fig. 4), Goodwin's brush-
302 tailed mice were generally distributed in the Kopet-Dag-Hezar Masjed, Binalud, Elburz-
303 Azarbijan, and Central Iran structural zones, with a variety of climates including cold mountain,
304 Mediterranean, cold semi-desert, and marginally in hot semi-desert. Hotson's brush-tailed mice,
305 however, were found primarily in the Flysch and Central Iran structural zones, with great habitat
306 suitability in hot dry desert, hot semi-desert and marginally in cold semi-desert climatic
307 conditions. *C. elburzensis* mainly inhabits in forest steppe, forests and woodlands, and semi-
308 desert biotopes, whereas *C. hotsoni* occupies forest steppe, semi-desert biotopes, and desert

309 lowlands. These findings are in agreement with previous findings reported by Hamidi et al.
310 (2016).

311 According to the predictive habitat distribution model, suitable areas for *C. elburzensis* to occur
312 were identified within the Irano-Turanian floristic region which mainly consists of different
313 types of steppe coniferous and flowering plants such as *Juniperus* L. and *Pistacia* L., and also
314 shrubs genera *Prunus* L., *Quercus* L., and *Astragalus* L., whereas predicted distribution for *C.*
315 *hotsoni* was mainly located within the Sudanian floristic region with the lower plant diversity
316 and low growing rate plant species, a coverage of flowering and small spiny trees and also
317 shrubs such as *Prosopis* L., *Tamarix* L., *Cyperus* L., and *Acacia* (Martius 1829) (Zohary 1973;
318 Noroozi et al. 2008). Dominant plant forms of predicted suitable habitats for *C. elburzensis*
319 included *Juniperus* steppe forest remnants, *Pistacia-Amygdalus* steppe forest and *Artemisia*
320 steppe, whereas for *C. hotsoni*, *Pistacia-Amygdalus* steppe forest, Saharo-Sindian *Acacia* steppe
321 forest and *Artemisia* steppe were identified as dominant vegetation forms (see Zohary 1973;
322 Noroozi et al. 2008 for vegetation characteristics and classification).

323 Iran has been divided into geomorphic units, each characterized by a relatively unique record of
324 magmatic activities, metamorphisms, tectonics, orogenic events, stratigraphy, and overall
325 geological appearance (see tectonic maps of Iran in Stocklin & Nabavi 1973; Nabavi 1976;
326 Alavi-Naini 1983; Aghanabati 2004). According to the niche modelling maps, suitable habitats
327 for *C. elburzensis* are mainly located in Northeastern Iran, Northern Iran and along the western
328 border of Central Iran geomorphic units, whereas habitat suitability for *C. hotsoni* is coincident
329 with the Eastern and Central Iran geomorphic units (Fig. 4). The Northeastern Iran (Kopet-Dag)
330 geomorphic unit was covered with a vast continental shelf sea during the Middle Jurassic and is
331 composed of a thick sequence of marine and continental sediments with no reports of major
332 sedimentary gap or volcanic activities. The Elburz range is located in Northern Iran geomorphic

333 unit which is characterized by the dominance of platform-type sediments. The Binalud zone is a
334 continuation of the Elburz range, located east of that range but has features comparable to those
335 of Central Iran geomorphic unit, where rocks of all ages and several episodes of metamorphism
336 and magmatism can be recognized. Finally, the Eastern Iran geomorphic unit is divided into two
337 parts: Lut Block and Flysch or colored mélange of Zabol-Baluch Zone (also called Nehbandan-
338 Khash Band). The Lut Block is the main body of the Eastern Iran geomorphic unit, located to the
339 west of the Flysch Zone and consists of schists overlain by limestone and other sedimentary
340 rocks. The Flysch Zone is located between the Lut Block to the west and Helmand (near Iran-
341 Afghanistan border) to the east. In contrast to Lut Block, the Flysch Zone is highly deformed and
342 tectonized; most rock units in this zone are flyschoid sediments, volcanic, volcano-sedimentary,
343 and intrusive rocks (Ghorbani 2013) (Fig. 4).

344 Geological and geomorphological conditions (such as soil type and hardness, soil moisture
345 content, metamorphism, and stratigraphy), climatic conditions (such as temperature, precipitation
346 and humidity), vegetation cover and density, dominant plants, and overall habitat structure and
347 macro-ecological conditions are different among these rocky areas inhabited by these two
348 species of brush-tailed mice and likely contributes to the different habitat requirements of these
349 two species.

350 *Contact zone and niche overlap*

351 While *C. elburzensis* and *C. hotsoni* both inhabit a wide range of environmental conditions
352 throughout their ranges and show little spatial overlap, probable contact zones have been
353 identified in northern center of both South Khorasan and Kerman provinces. In the two areas of
354 potential contact, climatic conditions were mainly identified as hot semi-deserts and cold semi-
355 deserts, with forest steppe and semi-desert biotopes including *Pistacia-Amygdalus* steppe forest
356 and *Artemisia* steppe as the dominant vegetation forms. The geographic distribution of these two

357 species in Iran is potentially parapatric based on the proximity of the ranges of the two species,
358 the homogeneous habitat separating the two, and the lack of an apparent geographic barrier.
359 Niche modelling analyses showed that these two species do not have a high degree of niche
360 similarities. Hence, it would be hypothesized that this is the evolutionary outcome of *C. hotsoni*
361 being in a southern clade which likely evolved in hotter and dry climates, whereas *C. elburzensis*
362 is part of a northern clade that evolved in milder climates. Although these two species do not
363 occupy very similar regions, their niches would have to be much more similar in the areas with
364 suitable climatic conditions and plant coverage for both. Moreover, making a case that the niche
365 separation between these two species would be much reduced in the areas of contact, where there
366 is high suitability for both to occur, is the key to lead into the inclusion of the competition
367 interaction.

368 *Habitat heterogeneity and productivity*

369 Habitat structure and primary productivity have important effects on the diversity of animal
370 communities (MacArthur 1964; Rosenzweig 1995). In more productive habitats, the greater plant
371 coverage, variety in vegetation cover and plant productivity influence the species diversity of
372 small mammals (Brown & Lieberman 1973; Abramsky & Rosenzweig 1984; Wang et al. 1999).
373 Greater plant resources, as indexed by plant coverage, may influence complexity of habitat
374 structure and would support greater species diversity, compared with poor habitats with sparse
375 vegetation (Reed et al. 2006; Zhong et al. 2016).

376 Recently, molecular analyses of *Cytb* and *COI* gene sequences have recovered four subclades of
377 *C. elburzensis* in northeast of Iran (Akbarirad et al. 2016b). A similar study, recovered only two
378 subclades of *C. hotsoni* in southeastern Iran (Akbarirad et al. 2016a). According to our niche
379 modelling and our previous findings (Hamidi et al. 2016), great differences in the climatic
380 conditions, geological characteristics, vegetation cover and overall habitat structure were

381 observed among areas inhabited by *C. elburzensis* in Iran, and populations of this species occur
382 in a range of biotopes. In contrast, little differences were observed among areas inhabited by *C.*
383 *hotsoni*. Herein, according to the productivity hypothesis (MacArthur 1972), it is predicted that
384 the more productive and diverse habitats with massy covers of different vegetation mainly on the
385 north and northeastern Iran could support greater intraspecific differentiation for *C. elburzensis*.
386 In contrast, lower intraspecific differentiation could be predicted for *C. hotsoni* living in the less
387 productive hot and dry habitats in southeast of Iran with sparse vegetation cover. With regards to
388 the greater intraspecific genetic distances reported for *C. elburzensis* as compared with *C.*
389 *hotsoni* throughout Iran (Akbarirad et al. 2016a, 2016b), it would be assumed that geographical
390 distances and the differences observed in some habitats of the first species may have influenced
391 these genetic distances.

392

393

CONCLUSION

394 Species distribution models provide a better understanding of a species ecological niche and the
395 present work provides useful knowledge on the areas of suitable environmental habitats where
396 two related species of brush-tailed mice do and could occur. Such predictions could also identify
397 localities for future field work and are also useful in following range shifts and changes in areas
398 of contact in response to climate changes. Characterizing the niche of these two species were
399 based primarily on climatological and geological variables as well as plant coverage. However,
400 other factors which may also be important in defining niche characteristics should be considered.
401 Herein, ecological distribution modelling of the two brush-tailed mice showed a low degree of
402 niche similarities. However, further studies are needed in the case of character displacement and
403 divergent niche evolution between *C. elburzensis* and *C. hotsoni*. Moreover, these ecological
404 niche models identified areas in the north center of both South Khorasan and Kerman provinces

405 suitable for these two species to co-occur. Studies on morphological and morphometric
406 differences (especially in their contact zones), which are important to investigate character
407 displacement for species identification associated with pre-mating isolation are suggested.
408 Finally, since dietary habits of sympatric or parapatric rodents partially determine their realized
409 ecological niches, stomach content analysis will be helpful in defining rodents' trophic positions
410 and the mechanism through which partitioning of niches and resources was occurred; for
411 example, using resources at different space or foraging of different food sizes.

412

413

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420

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460 [prospects/the-role-of-landscape-in-contact-zones-of-sister-species-of-lizard](http://www.intechopen.com/books/perspectives-on-nature-conservation-patterns-pressures-and-prospects/the-role-of-landscape-in-contact-zones-of-sister-species-of-lizard) [Accessed 29
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616 **Table legends**

617 Table 1.
 618 Coordinate records for two species of brush-tailed mice, *Calomyscus elburzensis* and *C. hotsoni*,
 619 used in the present study. ZMFUM: Zoology Museum of Ferdowsi University of Mashhad;
 620 FMNH: Field Museum of Natural History (Chicago, IL); MHNG: Muséum d’Histoire Naturelle
 621 de Genève; UF: University of Florida, Museum of Natural History. Data available on the web:
 622 NCBI at <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>, GBIF at <https://www.gbif.org/>, and VerNet at
 623 <http://www.vertnet.org/>.

No.	Longitude	Latitude	Locality	Museum/NCBI Accession No.	Reference(s)
Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (<i>C. elburzensis</i>)					
1	60.88	36.25	Aghdarband; Sarakhs; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	KT884549 ZMFUM1921	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
2	58.72	37.43	Tandure; Dargaz; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	KT884548 ZMFUM1675	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
3	59.57	36.25	Khaje Morad; Mashhad; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	KT878581 ZMFUM1542	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
4	54.32	31.66	Fakhr Abad; Yazd; Iran	KT878582 ZMFUM171	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
5	61.12	36.50	Aghdarband; Sarakhs; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	KT878585 ZMFUM1874	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
6	57.29	37.49	Dasht; Bojnord; North Khorasan; Iran	KT884579 ZMFUM1933	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
7	60.40	35.15	Shahneshin Mts.; Nasr Abad;	KT878587	Akbarirad et

			Torbat-e Jam; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	ZMFUM2088	al. 2016b
8	58.86	36.36	Soghand; Binalud Mts.; Neyshabour; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	KT884550 ZMFUM2148	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
9	58.41	36.35	Buzhan; Binalud Mts.; Neyshabour; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	KT884551 ZMFUM2152	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
10	58.17	34.40	Siahkuh; Bajestan; South Khorasan; Iran	KT884552 ZMFUM2195	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
11	57.37	37.42	Kurkhud; Bojnord; North Khorasan; Iran	KT878590 ZMFUM3533	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
12	57.90	37.34	Salook; Esfaraieen; North Khorasan; Iran	KT878588 ZMFUM2978	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
13	59.91	33.60	Shaskooh; Hajiabad; Ghaen; South Khorasan; Iran	KT884554 ZMFUM3305	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
14	60.11	33.04	Darmiyan; Birjand; South Khorasan; Iran	KT884558 ZMFUM4530	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
15	60.22	32.99	Gezik; Birjand; South Khorasan; Iran	KT884557 ZMFUM4529	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
16	57.18	36.52	Zarghan; Sabzevar; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	KT884556 ZMFUM4490	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
17	54.10	31.71	Fakhr Abad; Yazd; Iran	KT878584 ZMFUM1777	Akbarirad et al. 2016b

18	59.49	36.94	Kopet-Dag Mts.; Kalat; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	KY039480 ZMFUM5014	Hamidi et al. 2017
19	59.57	36.25	Khaje Morad; Mashhad; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	KT884547	Akbarirad et al. 2016a
20	48.59	36.12	Qeydar; Zanjan; Iran	ZMFUM3925	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
21	48.59	37.12	Qeydar; Zanjan; Iran	ZMFUM3937	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
22	51.77	33.45	Karkas; Isfahan; Iran	ZMFUM3938	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
23	59.69	36.14	Khaje Morad; Mashhad; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	ZMFUM5019	K. Hamidi unpublished data
24	59.69	36.14	Khaje Morad; Mashhad; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	ZMFUM5022	K. Hamidi unpublished data
25	54.08	31.65	Esmaeilieh; Yazd; Iran	ZMFUM1780	Haddadian Shad & Darvish 2018a
26	59.9	33.6	Bajestan; South Khorasan; Iran	ZMFUM2195	Haddadian Shad & Darvish 2018a
27	58.71	33.92	Barz Abad; Ghaen; South Khorasan; Iran	ZMFUM5048	Safapour 2017

28	57.43	37.93	Salook; Esfaraïen; North Khorasan; Iran	-	Akbarirad et al. 2015
29	54.15	31.65	Shirkuh Mts; Cheshme; Taft; Yazd; Iran	-	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
30	54.08	31.64	Shirkuh Mts; Ab-Mazrae; Taft; Yazd; Iran	-	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
31	54.08	31.65	Shirkuh Mts; Dare-Bidun; Taft; Yazd; Iran	-	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
32	57.16	37.16	Salook; Esfaraïen; North Khorasan; Iran	-	Akbarirad et al. 2015
33	54.42	31.41	Kuhe Bakhtaki; Mehriz; Yazd; Iran	-	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
34	56.52	37.44	Kurkhud; Bojnord; North Khorasan; Iran	-	Akbarirad et al. 2016b
35	58.53	37.36	Agh Mazar Abad; Maneh and Samalqan; North Khorasan; Iran	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
36	54.12	31.55	Godar Nir; Yazd; Iran	-	Haddadian Shad & Darvish 2018b
37	54.06	31.65	Cheshmeh Piazi; Yazd; Iran	-	Haddadian Shad & Darvish 2018b
38	54.41	31.4	Mehriz; Yazd; Iran	-	Haddadian

					Shad & Darvish 2018b Haddadian
39	54.1	31.7	Ta Mehr; Yazd; Iran	-	Shad & Darvish 2018b
40	57.93	37.33	Gelian; North Khorasan; Iran	-	Shahabi et al. 2010
41	58.79	35.51	Kashmar; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	-	GBIF/ VertNet
42	58.41	36.87	Quchan; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	-	GBIF/ VertNet
43	54.34	35.89	Semnan; Semnan; Iran	-	GBIF/ VertNet
44	59.53	36.91	Kopet-Dag Mts; Cheshme- Kabkan; Kalat; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	-	K. Hamidi unpublished data
45	59.35	36.91	Kopet-Dag Mts; Kaj-Darre; Kalat; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	-	K. Hamidi unpublished data
46	59.35	37.12	Tirgan; Dargaz; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	-	K. Hamidi unpublished data
47	59.36	37.09	Robat; Kalat; Razavi Khorasan; Iran	-	K. Hamidi unpublished data
48	57.2	37.36	Gachranlo; Bojnord; North	-	(VG. Malikov,

			Khorasan; Iran		personal communication)
49	56.51	37.43	Kurkhud; Bojnord; North Khorasan; Iran	-	(VG. Malikov, personal communication)
50	56.71	37.44	Darekesh; Bojnord; North Khorasan; Iran	-	(VG. Malikov, personal communication)
51	64.43	33.54	25 mi E Maimana, Fariab, Afghanistan	FMNH102973	Hassinger 1973
52	62.1	34.2	8 mi N Herat, Herat, Afghanistan	FMNH102977	Hassinger 1973
53	63.1	34.57	68 mi by road E Herat, Zarmast (Sauzak) Pass, Afghanistan	FMNH201980	Hassinger 1973
54	58.08	37.91	Fir'uza (14 km SW Ashgabat), Central Kopet-Dag, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
55	58.06	38.03	Chuli (36 km W Ashgabat), Central Kopet-Dag, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
56	58.83	37.75	Kalininsk, Central Kopet-Dag, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
57	57.43	38.38	5 km S Bakharden, Central Kopet-Dag, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000

58	58.71	37.81	G'aur's (36 km E Ashgabat), Central Kopet-Dag, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
59	59.61	37.35	Archenyan, Eastern Kopet- Dag, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
60	61.25	35.91	Akar-Chashme, Western Badkhyz, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
61	58.16	37.83	Summit Mt Dushak, Central Kopet-Dag, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
62	56.5	38.33	Ai-Dere, Western Kopet-Dag, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
63	56.28	38.96	Gyzylarbat, Western Kopet- Dag, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
64	55.66	39.16	Danata, Western Kopet-Dag, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
65	54.83	39.11	Little Balkhan Mountain, Turkmenistan	-	Graphodatsky et al. 2000
<hr/> <i>Hotson's brush-tailed mouse (Calomyscus hotsoni)</i> <hr/>					
66	58.69	32.92	Tejg; Ark heights; Birjand; South Khorasan; Iran	KY039482 ZMFUM5025	Hamidi et al. 2017
67	58.91	32.41	Hamech; Shadan and Olang heights; Birjand; South Khorasan; Iran	KY039483 ZMFUM5026	Hamidi et al. 2017
68	61.77	27.30	Birk Mts; Paskooh; Saravan;	KT884560	Akbarirad et

			Sistan and Baluchestan; Iran		al. 2016a
69	61.17	28.15	Abkhan Mts; Khash; Sistan and Baluchestan; Iran	KT884567	Akbarirad et al. 2016a
70	59.21	32.81	Bagheran Mts; Birjand; South Khorasan; Iran	KT884573	Akbarirad et al. 2016a
71	60.78	29.74	Malek Siahkuh Mts; Zahedan; Sistan and Baluchestan; Iran	KT884568	Akbarirad et al. 2016a
72	61.46	27.18	Saravan; Sistan and Baluchestan; Iran	ZMFUM 2102	Shahabi et al. 2010
73	58.86	32.44	Gound; Nehbandan; South Khorasan; Iran	ZMFUM5027	K. Hamidi unpublished data
74	57.24	30.04	Jupar; Kerman; Iran	MHNG1686.72	de Roguin 1988
75	57.19	29.33	Zahrud-e Bala; Kerman; Iran	MHNG1686.73	de Roguin 1988
76	61	28.34	Kusheh; Sistan and Baluchestan; Iran	MHNG1686.74	de Roguin 1988
77	57.49	26.50	Fanuj; Sistan and Baluchestan; Iran	-	Khajeh et al. 2015
78	58.04	28.60	Anbar Abad; Kerman; Iran	-	Khajeh et al. 2015
79	59.64	26.55	Kohe Heydar; Sardasht;	-	Khajeh et al.

			Bashagard; Hormozgan; Iran		2015
80	60.85	29.51	Zahedan; Sistan and Baluchestan; Iran	-	GBIF/ VertNet
81	60.36	26.39	Nikshahr; Sistan and Baluchestan; Iran	-	GBIF/ VertNet
82	61.25	28.35	Khash; Sistan and Baluchestan; Iran	-	GBIF/ VertNet
83	65.84	28.02	6 km E Wadh; Dancer; Khuzdar; Baluchestan; Pakistan	EU135583	Norris et al. 2008
84	64.15	26.76	Mitha Singh; Panjgur; Baluchestan; Pakistan	EU135579	Norris et al. 2008
85	66.88	26.38	Rani Kot; near Shergart Fort; Dadu; Sindh; Pakistan	EU135582	Norris et al. 2008
86	66.83	26.73	35 km W Dadu; Sindh; Pakistan	UF15092	Norris et al. 2008
87	64.09	26.96	Panjgur; Gwambuk; Pakistan	FMNH83058	GBIF/ VertNet

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Table 2.

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Bioclimatic variables used to develop the distribution models for Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse

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(Calomyscus elburzensis) and Hotson's brush-tailed mouse (*C. hotsoni*) in MaxEnt. Contribution

634

ratio (%) and permutation importance values for each layer are also shown.

Variable	Percentage contribution		Permutation	
	value		importance (%)	
	<i>C.</i> <i>elburzensis</i>	<i>C.</i> <i>hotsoni</i>	<i>C.</i> <i>elburzensis</i>	<i>C.</i> <i>hotsoni</i>
Bio2 (annual mean diurnal range)	8.78	0.05	8.6	1.58
Bio3 (isothermality)	–	55.52	–	16.03
Bio4 (temperature seasonality)	0.68	2.99	2.02	17.94
Bio5 (max temperature of warmest month)	–	–	–	–
Bio6 (min temperature of coldest month)	48.22	8.95	49.41	4.15
Bio8 (mean temperature of wettest quarter)	4.45	–	2.11	–
Bio9 (mean temperature of driest quarter)	–	1.22	–	10.12
Bio12 (annual precipitation)	0.46	23.58	3.56	34.32
Bio14 (precipitation of driest month)	–	–	–	–
Bio15 (precipitation seasonality)	–	0.14	–	0.59
Bio18 (precipitation of warmest quarter)	11.35	2.42	7.22	12.77
Bio19 (precipitation of coldest quarter)	26.06	5.13	27.08	2.5

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637 **Figure captions**

638

639 Fig. 1. — (A) Goodwin's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus elburzensis*). (B) Habitat and
640 vegetation cover of *C. elburzensis* in the Hezar Masjed-Allāho Akbar heights, Razavi Khorasan
641 province. (C) Hotson's brush-tailed mouse (*Calomyscus hotsoni*). (D) Habitat and vegetation
642 cover of *C. hotsoni* in the Shadan and Olang heights, Bagheran Mts, South Khorasan province.

643

644 Fig. 2. — Potential distribution map of *Calomyscus elburzensis*. Known localities for *C.*
 645 *elburzensis* and possible contact zones for *C. elburzensis* and *C. hotsoni* are shown as black dots
 646 and blue circles, respectively.

647

648 Fig. 3. — Potential distribution map of the *Calomyscus hotsoni*. Known localities for *C. hotsoni*
 649 and possible contact zones for *C. hotsoni* and *C. elburzensis* are shown as black dots and blue
 650 circles, respectively.

651

652 Fig. 4. — Tectonic map of Iran with approximate borders of four main geomorphic units in
 653 eastern and central Iran. Structural zones (also known as geomorphotectonic units) throughout
 654 Iran are shown in the map and listed in the legend; those which are indicated in bold are located
 655 in the four geomorphic units (reproduced from Nabavi 1976).